

The Effect of Transformational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Justice on Organizational Citizenship Behavior With Job Satisfaction as Intervening Variable

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Article history:

Received July 02, 2021; Accepted: August 24, 2021; Displayed Online: September 01, 2021; Published: December 30, 2021

Keywords

Perceived Organizational Justice;
Transformational Leadership;
Job Satisfaction;
Organizational Citizenship Behavior;

Abstract

The objectives of this research are (1) Analyzing the relationship of Transformational Leadership, Perceived Organizational Justice and Job Satisfaction on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (2) Seeing the influence of Leadership and Perceived Organizational Justice on Organizational Citizenship Behavior both directly and indirectly mediated by Job Satisfaction (3) Seeing the relationship between Transformational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Justice on Job Satisfaction (4) Seeing the relationship of Transformational Leadership on Perceived Organizational Justice. This research was conducted on 240 temporary employees who work for Complete systematic land registration of National Land Agency for the Special Capital Region of Jakarta. This research was conducted with a quantitative approach using a questionnaire. The data analysis used was Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using the SmartPLS 3.2.9 system. Based on the research results, it was known that Transformational Leadership, Perceived Organizational Justice and Job Satisfaction had a significant positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. Then, it was known that Job Satisfaction was able to mediate Transformational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Justice in a significant positive way on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. In addition, Transformational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Justice had a significant positive relationship toward Job Satisfaction.

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1. Introduction

Human resources are an important element for an organization. As an important asset for the company, the company must be able to have potential human resources. Potential employees can give their best performance for the company. In government organizations, the existing human resources consist of permanent employees and temporary employees. Temporary employees are often considered as employees who have low work commitment and also tend to have low Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Martinez et al, 2010).

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is an extra role behavior carried out by an employee voluntarily. Organizational Citizenship Behavior can be in the form of an employee's desire to work more than his main task, a desire to help colleagues or behavior to comply with existing regulations within the organization. OCB is an important part of an employee's behavior, where OCB behavior can make the organization more effective in achieving its goals, therefore OCB behavior is needed for every employee in an organization. OCB behavior in temporary employees who work for Complete systematic land registration of National Land Agency for the Special Capital Region of Jakarta was still said to be low, this was seen from the indiscipline of temporary employees at work. The following is the attendance data of temporary employees for the last 6 months

Table 1
Percentage of Temporary Employees Attendance of CSLR in August-December 2020

Month	Alpha (%)	Late (%)	Sick (%)
August	1.79%	3.57%	0.36%
September	2.14%	1.79%	1.43%
October	2.86%	1.07%	0.71%
November	2.86%	4.64%	0.36%
December	3.21%	6.79%	0.71%

Source: Human Resource Department of the National Land Agency for the Special Capital Region of Jakarta, 2020

Based on table 1, it can be seen that there were still quite a number of temporary employees who were undisciplined. This indicates that temporary employees had less OCB behavior. Therefore, it was necessary to know the cause of the low OCB behavior in temporary employees by distributing pre-research questionnaires to 40 temporary employees. From the results of the questionnaires given, it was found that there were 3 variables most chosen by temporary employees, they were Transformational Leadership, Perceived Organizational Justice, and Job Satisfaction. They assumed that these variables most influenced their OCB behavior.

Figure 1. Questionnaire results of factors that influence OCB behavior

Based on Figure 1, it is known that leadership is one of the factors considered by temporary employees as a variable that affects their OCB behavior. Moorhead & Griffin (2013) stated that Leadership is an influence to drive its members to achieve goals. Transformational leadership is a dynamic type of leadership. In public or government organizations, the role of the leader is very large in influencing and encouraging the behavior of his subordinates. There are various kinds of leadership styles, but transformational leadership is one of the appropriate leadership styles to be applied to leaders working in the public sector (Barth-Farkas & Vera, 2014; Gennaro, 2018; Wright & Pandey, 2009). Transformational leader is able to influence, motivate, stimulate and encourage employees to improve their abilities (Ugwu et al., 2020).

In addition to transformational leadership, perceived organizational justice is also one of the variables that are considered capable of influencing OCB behavior. Perceived Organizational Justice is an employee's perception of fairness in the organization such as whether they are sufficiently rewarded in return for their contribution and whether the employee is treated fairly procedurally and interpersonally. Employees will show a positive attitude towards the organization when they realize that their organization is fair to them (Imran et al., 2015). For this reason, it was very important for employees to have the same perceived organizational justice so that they can influence their organizational behavior in a better direction (Ince & Gül, 2011).

The justice received by employees also fosters job satisfaction in themselves, which will also affect the employee's OCB behavior. Employees who have low job satisfaction will tend to waste their time during working hours, this will also slowly reduce their OCB behavior so that it is no longer created in them (Imran et al, 2015). Therefore, job satisfaction is important for employees in improving their OCB behavior.

Based on this, it is necessary to know the influence of the variables of transformational leadership, perceived organizational justice, and job satisfaction on the Organizational Citizenship Behavior of temporary employees who work for Complete systematic land registration of National Land Agency for the Special Capital Region of Jakarta.

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Transformational Leadership has an effect on Perceived Organizational Justice

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- Hypothesis 2: Transformational Leadership has an effect on Job Satisfaction
- Hypothesis 3: Perceived Organizational Justice has an effect on Job Satisfaction
- Hypothesis 4: Job Satisfaction has an effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)
- Hypothesis 5: Transformational Leadership has an effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)
- Hypothesis 6: Perceived Organizational Justice has an effect Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)
- Hypothesis 7: Transformational has an effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) mediated by Job Satisfaction
- Hypothesis 8: Perceived Organizational Justice has an effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) mediated by Job Satisfaction

2. Research Method

This research was conducted by involving temporary employees of the Complete systematic land registration of National Land Agency for the Special Capital Region of Jakarta by distributing questionnaires via Google form. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling with a sample size of 240 employees. There were 48 statement indicators that should be answered by respondents on the questionnaire using a Likert scale of 1-5, starting from strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree and strongly agree. In this research, hypothesis testing was done by analyzing Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with Partial Least Square (PLS).

3. Results and Discussions

Based on the results of hypothesis testing by using smartPLS 3.2.9, a structural model between variables was generated as seen in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Structural Model

Hypothesis Test Results

The results of hypothesis testing based on Figure 2 above can be seen clearly in the following table:

Table 2
Hypothesis Test Results

	Hypothesis	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values
H1	Transformational Leadership → Perceived Organizational Justice	0.885	39.810	0.000
H2	Transformational Leadership → Job Satisfaction	0.337	4.701	0.000
H3	Perceived Organizational Justice → Job Satisfaction	0.620	8.729	0.000
H4	Job Satisfaction → Organization Citizenship Behavior	0.498	5.539	0.000
H5	Transformational Leadership → Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.241	2.806	0.005
H6	Perceived Organizational Justice → Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.220	2.716	0.007
H7	Transformational Leadership → Job Satisfaction → Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.168	3.537	0.000
H8	Perceived Organizational Justice → Job Satisfaction → Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.309	4.669	0.000

Discussions

1. Transformational Leadership with Perceived Organizational Justice

Table 2 shows that there was a positive and significant effect of Transformational Leadership on Perceived Organizational Justice which was indicated by the t-statistic value of $39.810 > 1.960$, and the p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$, thus Hypothesis H1 was accepted. This is in line with Azarsetan et al. (2013); Deschamps et al., (2016); and Ha & Le (2021) and Singhry (2018) who also found a positive effect of Transformational Leadership on Perceived Organizational Justice. Therefore, the higher the application of a transformational leadership, the higher the employee's perception of justice. On the contrary, the lower the application of transformational leadership, the lower the employee's perception of justice. Transformational leadership had an effect on employees' perceptions of justice they received from the organization (Pratikna, 2015). In addition, Raharjo & Witiastuti (2016) stated that high Perceived Organizational Justice was strongly influenced by the role of Transformational Leadership.

The higher the implementation of transformational leadership in the organization, the greater the perception of employee justice towards the organization. The leadership behavior itself could be in the form of giving the equal duties and responsibilities between temporary employees with one another, the opportunity for temporary employees to express their opinion, or the leaders' behavior

who is able to communicate well and be open to temporary employees. Therefore, the relationship between transformational leadership and all aspects of organizational justice was very strong (Deschamps et al., 2016).

Conversely, the low implementation of transformational leadership would result in low employee's perception of justice. Employees felt that the injustice given by transformational leaders would cause feelings of disappointment so that their perception of justice was reduced. Lack of concern from superiors would cause employee dissatisfaction, this often happened to government employees such as temporary employees of Complete systematic land registration of National Land Agency for the Special Capital Region of Jakarta who still had a strong bureaucracy, where leaders often asked for maximum work results. However, they were not paying attention to the needs of their subordinates, which caused employees feel pressured and dissatisfied at work. This described that the relationship between employees and their superiors could build the relationship between employees and the organization and a individual willingness to contribute to his superiors (Miao & Kim, 2010).

2. Transformational Leadership with Job Satisfaction

Table 2 shows that there as a positive and significant effect of Transformational Leadership on Job Satisfaction as indicated by the t-statistic value of $4.701 > 1.960$, and p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, Hypothesis H2 was accepted. The result of this research is in line with Puni et al. (2018); Abuelhassan & Nusari (2019); and Choi et al. (2020) who found that there was an effect of Transformational Leadership on Job Satisfaction. The higher the influence of transformational leadership, the higher the employees' job satisfaction. On the other hand, the lower the influence of transformational leadership, the lower the employees' job satisfaction. Transformational leadership could make subordinates satisfied with the company by encouraging subordinates with positive responses and giving praise to subordinates for their work (Lan et al., (2019).

Leaders appreciate and give appreciation to temporary employees in conducting their duties, where temporary employees are not only considered as a tool to achieve organizational goals but also realize the importance of the role of temporary employees in the sustainability of the program, especially in terms of administration and field assignments. This is in accordance with what is said by (Bogler, 2001) that transformational leaders can increase employee expectations and recognition of their work and increase employee job satisfaction through transformational leadership behaviors such as individual attention, intellectual stimulation, and motivation.

3. Perceived Organizational Justice with Job Satisfaction

Table 2 revealed that a positive and significant effect found between Perceived Organizational Justice on Job Satisfaction was taken from t-statistic value of $8.729 > 1.960$, and p-value of $0.007 < 0.05$; hence, Hypothesis H3 was accepted. This result had similar results with the research conducted by Kashif et al. (2016), Ajala (2017), and Altahayneh et al. (2017) who claimed that Perceived Organizational Justice had a significant and positive effect on employee job satisfaction. The higher the organizational justice was given, the higher the employee job satisfaction would be. The lower the organizational justice was given, the lower the job satisfaction of employees would be. Moreover, Mashii (2018) said that the employees more likely felt satisfied on their jobs if they get fair treatment. They improved their job satisfaction and got to work better. It was also in line with what Bazgir et al. (2018) stated that that organizational justice led to employee satisfaction.

4. Job Satisfaction with Organizational Citizenship Behavior

According to table 2, there was found a positive and significant effect of job satisfaction on the organizational citizenship behavior as it was indicated by t-statistic value of $5.539 > 1.960$, and p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$; so that Hypothesis H4 was accepted. This research results were in line with what Margahana et al. (2018), Pio & Tampi (2018), and Alkhadher et al. (2020) found that job satisfaction had an effect on OCB. The higher the employee's job satisfaction was obtained, the higher the employee's OCB behavior would be. The lower the employee's job satisfaction was obtained, the lower the employee's OCB behavior would be. The employees who felt satisfied with their jobs more likely engage in OCB by doing an extra work in the organization, were less likely to engage in deviant behavior and were expected to stay in the organization in a longer period of time (Mashi, 2018).

The respondents of this research obtained high job satisfaction from various aspects covering the satisfaction with colleagues and superiors, and the satisfaction with the job itself. Gyekye & Haybatollahi (2015) stated that if someone got lower job satisfaction, they were likely to have less motivation in actively participating in citizenship behavior (OCB).

5. Transformational Leadership with Organizational Citizenship Behavior

As what was shown in Table 2, a positive and significant effect of Transformational Leadership on the Organizational Citizenship Behavior was indicated by t-statistic value of $2.805 > 1.960$, and p-value of $0.005 < 0.05$; thus, Hypothesis H5 was accepted. The results of this research were in relation with the one done by Majeed et al. (2017), Han et al. (2016), and Khan et al. (2020) who found that transformational leadership laid on the organizational citizenship behavior. The higher the effect of transformational leadership that was performed, the higher their OCB behavior would be. The lower the effect of transformational leadership that was performed, the lower their OCB behavior would be. The implementation of transformational leadership style increased the employee morale at work and their willingness to work more than the expectation and raised OCB behavior in themselves (Majeed et al., 2017).

The respondents of this research felt that leader played an important role in affecting them to do their jobs; it included the way the leaders directed and supported them in their work, the involvement of leaders in work and the leaders who appreciated the employees' work made them want to work more than what had been expected, so that OCB behavior enlightened the employees. It was in line with what Kim & Park (2019) said that the transformational leadership was able to improve OCB behavior in employees.

6. Perceived Organizational Justice with Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Table 2 showed that the significant effect between Perceived Organizational Justice on Organization Citizenship Behavior was indicated by t-statistic value of $2.716 > 1.960$, and p-value of $0.001 < 0.07$; thus Hypothesis H6 was accepted. This research had the same results with the one carried out by Awang & Ahmad (2015), Latif & Pamikasih (2020), and Bazgir et al. (2018) who claimed that there was a significant and positive effect between Perceived Organizational Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). The higher the organizational justice given, the higher the employee's OCB behavior would be. The lower the justice given by the organization, the lower the OCB behavior shown by the employees would be. The higher the perception of justice possessed by employees towards the organizational justice, the higher the OCB behavior possessed by the employees would be (Ardi & Sudarma, 2015).

The respondents of this research showed Perceived Organizational Justice in fairly high level especially in the perceptions of procedural justice, in which the fair treatment given by the organization to each temporary employee impacted their OCB behavior. It was in line with what Latif & Pamikasih (2020) said that employees who felt highly appreciated as part of the organization had the perceptions of procedural justice so that the OCB shown to the organization tended to be high.

7. Transformational Leadership, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Job Satisfaction

Table 2 revealed that there was found a positive and significant effect of Transformational Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Job Satisfaction as it was indicated by the t-statistic value of $3.537 > 1.960$, and p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$; so that, Hypothesis H7 was accepted. The results of this research were in accordance with the research done by Nasra & Heilbrunn (2014), Ahmad & Jameel (2020) and Asgari et al. (2019) who said that Transformational Leadership had a significant and indirect effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through job satisfaction. The higher the effect of transformational leadership given to the employees, the higher the job satisfaction of employees would be; in which it impacted the employees' OCB behavior that was higher. The lower the effect of transformational leadership given to the employee, the lower the job satisfaction of employees would be; as it impacted the employee's OCB behavior that was lower.

The respondents of this research perceived that the implementation of leaders in the Complete systematic land registration Program of National Land Agency for the Special Capital Region of Jakarta who had a high concern for their employees, was able to support, motivate and appreciate their subordinates. This support was given by the leaders to their subordinates and was needed by employees in dealing with working dynamics. The employees felt that their needs were fulfilled so that their job satisfaction was also stimulated. The satisfaction felt by employees then triggered them to do an extra work and foster their OCB behavior meeting the work standards regulated by the organization. The increase on job satisfaction obtained from better co-worker relationships led to the higher level of team commitment, and fostered the overall volume of OCB behavior existed within the organizations (Foote & Tang, 2008). Thus, the conclusion drawn was that the implementation of transformational leadership was able to meet the needs of employees and enhance the employees' job satisfaction as well as their OCB behavior.

8. Perceived Organizational Justice, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Job Satisfaction

According to table 2, there was found a positive and significant effect of Perceived Organizational Justice on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Job Satisfaction as indicated by the t-statistic value of $4.669 > 1.960$, and p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$; hence, Hypothesis H8 was accepted. This research obtained the results which were found to be likely the same with a research done by Mashi (2018), Rauf (2015) and Junru & Huang (2019) who claimed that job satisfaction was able to mediate the relationship between Perceived Organizational Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. The higher the justice given by the organization, the higher the job satisfaction of employees would be as it made the employees reach the OCB higher. The lower the justice given by the organization, the lower the job satisfaction behavior of employees would be as the OCB behavior shown by the employees was lower.

The results of hypothesis verification were also supported by the results of descriptive statistical on the variables of Perceived Organizational Justice, Job Satisfaction and Organization Citizenship Behavior which revealed that the most of the respondents answered "agree" on those three variables whose mean value of their answers were in high interval (total mean 3.64 on

Perceived Organizational Justice, 3.59 on Job Satisfaction and 3.76 on Organizational Citizenship Behavior). The employees who felt that the justice given by the organization would provide them feedback and had them stimulated to behave OCB. As the justice was given to the employees through the attitude shown by the organization to them, it made the employees feel that what they did was equal to the justice given to their performance so that they involved themselves in OCB behavior that was beneficial for the organization. Furthermore, Bazgir et al. (2018) said that the organizational justice brought out the employees' satisfaction which played an important role in promoting OCB.

4. Conclusion

Reflecting on what has been presented above, several conclusions are stated as follows:

1. There was an effect between transformational leadership with perceived organizational justice
2. There was an effect between transformational leadership with job satisfaction
3. There was an effect between perceived organizational justice and job satisfaction
4. There was an effect between job satisfaction with Organizational Citizenship Behavior
5. There was an effect between transformational leadership with Organizational Citizenship Behavior
6. There was an effect between perceived organizational justice with Organizational Citizenship Behavior
7. There was an effect between transformational leadership with Organizational Citizenship Behavior through job satisfaction
8. There was an effect between perceived organizational justice with Organizational Citizenship Behavior through job satisfaction

Acknowledgements

The authors express their gratitude and appreciation to the publisher and reviewers who have reviewed and suggested the valuable suggestions, as well as have received the paper to be published.

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